

Survey Questionnaire

1. How often (how many days per week) and which services do you use?

	Do not use	1 day	2 days	3 day	4 days	5 days	6 days	Every day
ChatGPT	<input type="radio"/>							
Gemini	<input type="radio"/>							
Claude	<input type="radio"/>							
Grok	<input type="radio"/>							
Perplexity	<input type="radio"/>							
Le Chat	<input type="radio"/>							
Mistral	<input type="radio"/>							
Whisper	<input type="radio"/>							
DeepSeek	<input type="radio"/>							
Suno AI	<input type="radio"/>							
ElevenLab	<input type="radio"/>							
Canva	<input type="radio"/>							
Leonardo AI	<input type="radio"/>							
Heygen	<input type="radio"/>							
Runway	<input type="radio"/>							
Midjourney	<input type="radio"/>							
Gamma	<input type="radio"/>							

2. What purposes do you usually use AI services for?

- writing essays and summaries
- translating texts
- searching for information
- creating images
- creating software code
- solving coursework and exam assignments in academic subjects
- searching for academic sources and creating reference lists
- idea generation industry based on automation and robotics

3. How do you assess the accuracy and usefulness of the results obtained using artificial intelligence?

	1	2	3	4	5	
Very bad	<input type="radio"/>	Excellent				

4. How would you rate your level of proficiency in the main AI services you use most often?

- beginner
- novice (low intermediate)
- intermediate
- advanced
- expert

5. Do you think you use artificial intelligence in the educational process responsibly?

- yes, I use artificial intelligence in a fully responsible way
- yes, but I sometimes doubt whether it is always responsible
- not fully responsibly
- no, I use artificial intelligence in a completely irresponsible way
- I do not use artificial intelligence in education

6. Do you think the university should develop a policy regarding the use of artificial intelligence in the teaching process?

- yes
- no
- I don't know

7. How do you assess the importance of following ethical principles (transparency, responsibility, honesty) when using artificial intelligence?

	1	2	3	4	5	
It doesn't matter at all	O	O	O	O	O	Very important

8. Do you think that the use of artificial intelligence can negatively affect the development of your critical thinking?

- yes
- no
- hard to say
- I do not know what "critical thinking" is

9. What do you think are the main advantages of using artificial intelligence in education?

- personalized learning
- time savings
- access to new resources
- improved learning outcomes
- development of critical thinking and creativity
- instant feedback
- learning based on big data
- increased accessibility of education
- interactivity and engagement
- preparation for the future

10. What are the main risks you see in the use of artificial intelligence in the educational process?

- reduced critical thinking
- academic integrity violations
- insufficient contextual interpretation and incorrect data interpretation
- unequal access to AI technologies
- excessive automation and interference in the educational process
- dependence on technology
- privacy and security issues
- limitation of creativity

Characteristics of respondents

1. Which country are you from?

- Poland
- Ukraine

2. Your higher education institution?

3. What field of study (major) are you studying?

4. Year of study?

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6